

Product Subjective Sustainability:

Comparative Analysis of Psychological Lifetime of Short-lived and Long-lived Products through *Kansei* Engineering Approach

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Abstract: This research deals with the matter of subjective or psychological lifetime of products. Most scholar works concerning such a matter have considered user-product attachment as the only means being effective for extending the subjective lifetime of products. Aiming to analytically expand this means and/or to find out the other possible effective means in this regard, here, we have conducted a comparative and analytical study on the evolution of users' *Kansei* toward a short-lived and long-lived product during the entire lifecycles of those two kinds of product. As *Kansei* in its professional definition embraces all subjective issues of product, this research is based on *Kansei* Engineering approach. In this research, the product lifecycle from user perspective is divided into three different stages including purchasing/choosing, keeping/using and replacing/throwing away the product. Mobile phone, private passenger car and handicraft or Japanese traditional furniture are assigned respectively as the short-lived and long-lived products for investigation. Three groups of Japanese subjects, as the user or owner of these three kinds of product, are investigated and the changes of their *Kansei* toward their products are analyzed. The outcome of this analysis will be the *Kansei* factors associating with the investigated groups of subjects' rationale when purchasing, keeping/using and replacing their short/long-lived products. Finally, the extracted patterns and trends of the *Kansei* evolution of those three groups regarding their short/long-lived products during the lifecycle stages of those products are compared.

Key words: *Kansei Evolution, Attachment, Mobile Phone, Passenger Car, Handicraft.*

1. Introduction

The key challenge of “subjective environmental aspects of products and processes” has been discussed in design research since the last decade [1]. The given importance to the subjective issues of sustainability within the design researches is increasing theoretically and empirically. The topic of enhancing sustainability through human-factors design is also receiving growing attention, as the current studies of affective engineering systems, tools and methods, aimed generally at the more effective design of appealing products, would be relevant to design for sustainability [2]. Practically, the main focus of design researches concerning the subjective issues of sustainability is on ‘lifetime optimization of products’ [3]. On the basis of the results of analysis of the factors influencing the users’ decision for product replacement, Nes and Cramer propose five design strategies for

product longevity including: design for reliability and robustness; design for repair and maintenance; design for upgradeability; design for product attachment and design for variability. They emphasize that “the main challenge in design for longevity lies in achieving an enduring satisfaction with the product, rather than only meeting the momentary desires of today” [4].

‘Product attachment’ simply is defined as “the emotional bond experienced with a product” [5]. Many design researchers argue that extending the psychological life span of durables as well as increasing the degree of consumer-product attachment could be instrumental to reduce the demand for scarce resources and the rate of solid waste disposal and may contribute to a more sustainable society; because a stronger emotional bond between a consumer and his/her product will decrease the consumer’s tendency to dispose it and hence may result in a decrease of unnecessary waste and in a decreased use of limited resources of energy and materials [5,6,7,8]. The strategy to enhance product attachment is however the most uncertain in actually enhancing product longevity. As this strategy is based on the fact that the disposal of products is made harder when one feels attached to the product, it brings so many questionable points and challenges implying that it should be well considered and applied delicately [4]. Furthermore, it seems that product attachment is just one of the means for extending the psychological lifetime of products or optimizing product lifetime subjectively (ie affectively, emotionally and/or aesthetically). A product, even a very personal one like mobile phone device, may be emotionally pleasurable, aesthetically appealing and/or functionally comfortable during its expected short/long lifespan while there may not be any strong user-product-attachment. Moreover, durability of users’ satisfaction and emotional pleasure regarding a product and its appeal may be eventuated to attachment but not necessarily. Thus, user-product-attachment may be just a part of the product subjective issues including the user’s total image, feeling, affection, emotion, attitude and/or appreciation, which could be called *Kansei* about a product [9,10]. Therefore, there is seemingly a room for an open concept or wide expression to comprehensively encompass the subjective issues influencing product psychological lifetime and pleasurable longevity, for instance ‘Product Subjective Sustainability’ (PSjS) indicating “a product’s capability of being pleasing, appealing and satisfyingly lasting during its expected long/short lifetime” [11,12]. However, such a concept could be expanded to generally embrace all subjective issues of product reflecting, effecting and/or affecting sustainability values.

Keeping the above as the background and aiming at expanding PSjS experimentally, this paper presents the process and result of a comparative and analytical study done on the evolution of users’ *Kansei* – totally including feeling, emotion, image, attitude, etc – toward a short-lived product and a long-lived one during the entire lifecycles of those products. To cover all of the subjective issues of product, the survey and analysis in this research would be based on *Kansei* Engineering approach [13]. Considering the following points, mobile phone, private passenger car and handicraft or Japanese traditional furniture are respectively designated as the short-lived and long-lived product types for this analytical study. The subjective issues in mobile phone are more considerable than the other kinds of product due to the users’ very close/personal relation with it despite being a short-lived product [14,15]. Furthermore, user’s emotional attachment to mobile phone – rather than the other kinds of product – is reflected in numerous scholarly works [16,17,18,19]. There is also a considerable level of attachment between a user and his/her own car [8]. Private passenger car is an approximately long-lived product, as its increasingly average lifespan is about 12 years in Tokyo in 2009 [20]. As a private passenger car registers its owner’s individual character and social class, a user may have a personal relation with his/her car. But the Japanese traditional handicraft objects or furniture are defiantly long-lived product which are very valuable and

respectable for the owners of such objects. Nevertheless, these three product types completely vary when considering their scale beside user, technology, mobility, status, and function.

2. Methodology

In this analytical study the entire lifecycle of product from user perspective is divided into three main stages including: Purchase (P); Keep/Use (KU); and end, throw away or Replace (R). To find out and classify three groups of subjects' responded *Kansei* descriptive words regarding each lifecycle stage of their mobile phones, private cars or handicraft/furniture and thereupon extracting the various patterns of the subjects' *Kansei* evolutions during the lifecycle of these three kinds of product, this analytical study has been accomplished within three main steps. In the first step, survey, three groups of Japanese subjects (as user/owner of mobile phone, passenger car and handicraft/furniture) are investigated through the definite and extensive-descriptive questionnaire. The second step is the process and analysis of the data derived from the questionnaires by using KJ Method, Quantification Theory Type III (QT3) and Cluster Analysis. Last, in the third step, the results of analysis are interpreted and compared.

The first group of subjects, as the users of mobile phone, consists of 19 Japanese students of Chiba University ranging from 21 to 24 years. The second group consists of 18 Japanese owners of private car ranging from 40 to 60 years. And the third group consists of 15 Japanese owners of Japanese handicraft object or traditional furniture ranging from 38 to 74 years. Those three groups are investigated about their *Kansei* regarding their mobile phone, passenger car or handicraft/furniture in each of its three lifecycle stages (P, KU and R) separately within three different questions.

The *Kansei* descriptive words responded by the subjects are summarized into the *Kansei* items by using KJ Method through a discussion meeting held by the authors. After processing the data by using QT3, the method of Cluster Analysis is used for grouping the *Kansei* items and the subjects on the basis of their *Kansei* regarding their sort/long-lived products in the three lifecycle stages of those products. The choice of cut-off lines for the clustering algorithm are carefully made in order to arrive at the most meaningful groupings for understanding of the relationship between various *Kansei* items and also the subjects' *Kansei* statuses in the lifecycle stages of their products. The various patterns of the subjects' *Kansei* evolution would be eventually extracted from the resulted groupings relevant to their *Kansei* statuses in the lifecycle stages of their products.

3. Results

In the following sets of resulted graphs of distribution relevant to both the *Kansei* items and the subjects' *Kansei* statuses in the lifecycle stages of their sort/long-lived products, the different point shapes and colors are used for either illustrating the lifecycle stage (P, KU or R) each item associates rather with than the other stages or representing the subjects' *Kansei* status in each of the three lifecycle stages. This suggested association is decided on the basis of the frequencies of each item in the lifecycle stages. Regarding each of the sort/long-lived products designated for this analytical study, as both sets of the resulted distribution graphs are the output ("sample score" and "category score") of QT3 analysis on the same input data, these distribution graphs can be overlapped. The same names are therefore given to the axis directions of both sets of distribution graphs relevant to each product. All of the names given to the graphs' axis directions and clusters are decided on basis of the distribution of *Kansei* items in the graphs and the *Kansei* items belonging to each cluster.

3.1. Kansei Evolution in Mobile Phone Lifecycle

Nineteen subjects have responded in total 349 different Japanese keywords for their *Kansei* about their mobile phone in its different lifecycle stages: 153 ones for P stage; 140 ones for KU stage; and 56 ones for R stage. All these 349 keywords are summarized into 43 *Kansei* items through KJ Method. The subjects' responded *Kansei* keywords regarding all three lifecycle stages are adapted to these 43 *Kansei* items and processed by using QT3. The overall output distribution of the 43 *Kansei* items in terms of the lifecycle stages of mobile phone is shown into two graphs (X-Y and X-Z) in Figure 1. Using the resulted X, Y and Z dimensions, the chosen cut-off for the clustering algorithm has yielded seven clusters marked from *C.m1* to *C.m7* in the X-Y graph and four clusters marked from *G.m1* to *G.m4* in the X-Z one. The *Kansei* items and their clusters are listed in Table 1. The directions of the three axis of X, Y and Z are respectively named as 'Active Emotion-Passive Affection', 'Emotional-Rational' and 'Edgily/Affected-Lively/Pleased'. The highlighted clusters (*C.m1* to *C.m7*) in the X-Y graph can be characterized respectively as Fond, Attached, Ally (or Partner), Fresh-feel, Valid, Joy, and Bother. Similarly, the ones of the X-Z graph (*G.m1* to *G.m4*) can be characterized respectively as Attached, Joy/Fresh, Ally and Concerns. As the graphs show, the items located in the left or right sides respectively associate more with the lifecycle stage of P or R.

Figure 1. Distribution graphs (X-Y and X-Z) and groupings of the *Kansei* items relevant to Mobile Phone

Table 1. The *Kansei* items and their clusters relevant to Mobile Phone

Cluster	X-Z	X-Y	Kansei Items
	G.m4	C.m5	Accustom
	G.m4	C.m7	Anger
	G.m4	C.m7	Anxiety
	G.m3	C.m3	Appreciation
	G.m1	C.m2	Attachment
	G.m4	C.m7	Boring
	G.m2	C.m4	Cheap
	G.m1	C.m5	Cherished
	G.m4	C.m7	Complain
	G.m4	C.m7	Complication
	G.m4	C.m6	Curiosity
	G.m4	C.m6	Desire
	G.m2	C.m4	Discovery
	G.m4	C.m7	Dislike
	G.m4	C.m7	Dreary
	G.m4	C.m6	Easy
	G.m2	C.m4	Excite
	G.m1	C.m2	Familiarity
	G.m4	C.m7	Flaw
	G.m4	C.m7	Functional
	G.m4	C.m6	Good-look
	G.m4	C.m7	GUI/Hike
	G.m1	C.m1	Idol
	G.m4	C.m5	Important
	G.m4	C.m5	Longevity
	G.m1	C.m5	Lost
	G.m1	C.m1	Lovely
	G.m1	C.m2	Nostalgic
	G.m4	C.m7	Novelty
	G.m4	C.m7	Old Style
	G.m3	C.m3	Partner
	G.m4	C.m6	Pleasure
	G.m2	C.m4	Power Impress
	G.m4	C.m7	Puzzled
	G.m4	C.m7	Reasonable
	G.m2	C.m4	Refresh
	G.m4	C.m5	Regret-Wasteful
	G.m4	C.m7	Superfluous
	G.m2	C.m4	Surprise
	G.m3	C.m3	Tattered
	G.m4	C.m7	Temporary
	G.m2	C.m6	Toy
	G.m4	C.m7	Uniqueness

In order to delineate the changes of the subjects' *Kansei* toward their mobile phone during its lifecycle (namely P, KU and R stages), the X-Y and X-Z axis graphs of distribution of the subjects' *Kansei* status in the lifecycle stages are shown in Figure 2. The resulted clusters are marked from *Am* to *Em* and *Fm* to *Im* in the graphs respectively relevant to X-Y and X-Z axis. According to the items responded by majority of subjects belonging to each cluster, the highlighted clusters (*Am* to *Em*) in the X-Y graph can be characterized respectively as Bother, Valid, Joy/Fresh, Ally, and Attached. Similarly, the ones of the X-Z graph (*Fm* to *Im*) can be characterized respectively as Concerns, Joy/Fresh, Attached and Ally. The clusters, in which each subject (*S_i*) is laid during each stage (P, KU or R), are listed in Table 2.

Figure 2. Distribution graphs and groupings of the subjects' *Kansei* status in lifecycle of their Mobile Phones

Table 2. The clusters to which a subject belongs in each lifecycle stage of his/her Mobile Phone

	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	S ₁₆	S ₁₇	S ₁₈	S ₁₉
P	CGm	CGm	AFm	CGm	CGm	CGm	AFm	AFm	AFm	CGm	AFm	AFm	CGm	AFm	AFm	AFm	AFm	AFm	AFm
KU	EHm	AFm	AFm	BHm	AFm	EHm	AFm	AFm	AFm	AFm	AFm	DIm	AFm	AFm	AFm	AFm	AFm	BFm	AFm
R	EHm	AFm	BHm	DIm	DIm	EHm	AFm	AFm	EHm	DIm	AFm	DIm	AFm	EHm	AFm	DIm	AFm	BHm	BFm

3.2. *Kansei* Evolution in Private Car Lifecycle

Eighteen subjects have responded in total 430 Japanese keywords for their *Kansei* about their passenger car in its different lifecycle stages: 135 ones for P stage; 163 ones for KU stage; and 132 ones for R stage. These 430 keywords are summarized into 47 *Kansei* items. The subjects' responded *Kansei* keywords regarding all three lifecycle stages are adapted to these 47 *Kansei* items and processed by using QT3. The overall output distribution of the 47 *Kansei* items in terms of the lifecycle stages of private passenger car is shown into two graphs (X-Y and X-Z) in Figure 3. The resulted clusters are marked from C.v1 to C.v7 in X-Y graph and from G.v1 to G.v7 in X-Z graph. The *Kansei* items and their clusters are listed in Table 3. The directions of the three axis of X, Y and Z are respectively named as 'Active Emotion-Passive Affection', 'Satisfaction-Dissatisfaction' and 'Rational/Dissociate-Emotional/Associate'. The highlighted clusters (C.v1 to C.v7) in the X-Y graph can be characterized respectively as Lively Pleased, Lonely Grateful, Valid Object, Attached, Foreign, Displeasing and Trouble. The ones of the X-Z graph (G.v1 to G.v7) can also be characterized respectively as Attached, Affected, Valid, Practical Relation, Concerned, Joy/Fresh and Sorrowful Parting. As the graphs show, the items located in the left or right sides respectively associate more with the stage of P or R.

Figure 3. Distribution graphs (X-Y and X-Z) and groupings of the *Kansei* items relevant to Private Car

Table 3. The *Kansei* items and their clusters relevant to Private Car

Cluster	X-Z	X-Y	<i>Kansei</i> Items
	Gv1	Cv14	Accustomed
	Gv5	Cv16	Anxiety
	Gv4	Cv14	Apology/Shy
	Gv7	Cv12	Appreciate
	Gv1	Cv14	Attachment
	Gv3	Cv13	Beauty/Interested
	Gv4	Cv13	Comfort-ability
	Gv1	Cv14	Communicating
	Gv6	Cv1	Curiosity
	Gv4	Cv14	Defect/Flaw
	Gv6	Cv1	Enjoyed
	Gv6	Cv1	Excitation
	Gv6	Cv1	Excited
	Gv1	Cv14	Family/Relation
	Gv5	Cv16	Fastidious
	Gv6	Cv1	Freshness
	Gv5	Cv13	Frane-Features
	Gv3	Cv13	Habitual
	Gv6	Cv1	Happy
	Gv3	Cv13	Important/careful
	Gv2	Cv12	Indebted
	Gv3	Cv13	Individuality
	Gv4	Cv14	Longevity
	Gv7	Cv12	Lost/Missed
	Gv4	Cv14	Memories
	Gv6	Cv15	No-acustomed
	Gv2	Cv12	Nostalgic
	Gv1	Cv14	No-pleasant
	Gv6	Cv1	Novelty
	Gv1	Cv14	Old
	Gv7	Cv12	Painful
	Gv1	Cv14	Partner
	Gv1	Cv14	Pet
	Gv4	Cv12	Poor/pitiful
	Gv4	Cv13	Positive/logic
	Gv4	Cv16	Pout
	Gv7	Cv12	Regret
	Gv1	Cv14	Repair
	Gv5	Cv11	Satisfied
	Gv3	Cv13	Social/Solidarity
	Gv6	Cv15	Strange/Odd
	Gv3	Cv13	Strong-feel
	Gv4	Cv14	Tattered/scratched
	Gv4	Cv17	Trouble/Difficulty
	Gv5	Cv16	Uncomforted
	Gv4	Cv14	Utility
	Gv7	Cv12	Wasteful/too good

The graphs (X-Y and X-Z) of distribution of the subjects' *Kansei* status in the lifecycle stages of their car are shown in Figure 4. The resulted clusters are marked from Av to Fv in X-Y graph and from Gv to Kv in X-Z graph. According to the items responded by majority of subjects belonging to each cluster, the highlighted clusters (Av to Fv) in the X-Y graph can be characterized respectively as Attached, Lonely Grateful, Lively Satisfied, Pleasant Valid, Displeased and Concerned. Similarly, the ones of the X-Z graph (Gv to Kv) can be characterized respectively as Appreciated Utility, Satisfying Utility, Lively Valid, Affective Relation (Attachment) and Sorrowful Parting/Appreciation. The clusters in which each subject is laid during each stage are listed in Table 4.

Figure 4. Distribution graphs and groupings of the subjects' *Kansei* status in lifecycle of their Private Cars

Table 4. The clusters to which a subject belongs in each lifecycle stage of his/her Private Car

	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	S ₁₆	S ₁₇	S ₁₈
P	D _{1v}	C _{1v}	D _{2v}	D _{1v}	F _{1v}	D _{1v}	D _{1v}	C _{1v}	D _{2v}	D _{1v}	F _{1v}	E _{1v}	D _{1v}	F _{1v}	F _{1v}	C _{1v}	E _{1v}	C _{1v}
KU	F _{2v}	A _{1v}	A _{2v}	B _{2v}	A _{2v}	A _{2v}	A _{2v}	D _{2v}	A _{2v}	A _{2v}	A _{2v}	A _{2v}	F _{2v}	A _{2v}				
R	A _{3v}	B _{3v}	A _{3v}	F _{3v}	A _{3v}	A _{3v}	A _{3v}	B _{3v}	A _{3v}	A _{3v}	A _{3v}	D _{3v}	A _{3v}	D _{3v}	D _{3v}	A _{3v}	A _{3v}	B _{3v}

3.3. *Kansei* Evolution in Handicraft/Furniture Lifecycle

Fifteen subjects have responded in total 269 Japanese keywords for their *Kansei* about their handicraft/furniture in its different lifecycle stages: 119 ones for P stage; 90 ones for KU stage; and 60 ones for R stage. These 269 keywords are summarized into 35 *Kansei* items. The subjects' responded *Kansei* keywords regarding all three lifecycle stages are adapted to these 35 *Kansei* items and processed by using QT3. The overall output distribution of these *Kansei* items in terms of the lifecycle stages of handicraft/furniture is shown into two graphs (X-Y and X-Z) in Figure 5. The resulted clusters are marked from C.h1 to C.h6 in X-Y graph and from G.h1 to G.h4 in X-Z graph. The *Kansei* items and their clusters are listed in Table 5. The directions of the three axis of X, Y and Z are respectively named as 'Active Emotion-Passive Affection', 'Proximate Attraction-Ultimate Satisfaction' and 'Rational-Emotional'. The highlighted clusters (C.h1 to C.h6) in the X-Y graph can be characterized respectively as Interesting Durability, Practical Pleasant, Attachment/Concern, Cherish, Gratification and Nostalgic/Regret. The ones of the X-Z graph (G.h1 to G.h4) can also be characterized respectively as Nostalgic/Regret,

Durable/Pleasant Efficiency, Satisfying Attachment and Practical Concern. As the graphs show, the items located in the left or right sides respectively associate more with the stage of P or R.

Figure 5. Distribution graphs (X-Y and X-Z) and groupings of the *Kansei* items relevant to Handicraft/Furniture

Table 5. The *Kansei* items and their clusters relevant to Handicraft/Furniture

Cluster	Kansei Items	
	X-Y	X-Z
G.h4	C.h2	Customized
G.h3	C.h3	Anxiety
G.h1	C.h6	Apology
G.h2	C.h1	Appeal
G.h3	C.h5	Appreciated
G.h3	C.h3	Attached
G.h2	C.h2	Beautiful
G.h3	C.h4	Cherished
G.h4	C.h2	Convenient
G.h2	C.h2	Efficient
G.h2	C.h2	Enhanced
G.h2	C.h2	Fresh/Novel
G.h2	C.h2	Glad
G.h4	C.h2	Good-look
G.h2	C.h2	Harmonic
G.h2	C.h1	High Quality
G.h2	C.h2	Increasing Value
G.h2	C.h1	Interested
G.h2	C.h1	Longevity
G.h4	C.h2	Material
G.h4	C.h1	No-boring
G.h1	C.h6	Nostalgic
G.h4	C.h4	Old
G.h2	C.h2	Proportions
G.h4	C.h4	Realistic
G.h4	C.h2	Reasonable
G.h1	C.h6	Regretful
G.h2	C.h2	Relax
G.h3	C.h3	Reminiscent
G.h3	C.h5	Satisfied
G.h2	C.h1	Secure/Reliable
G.h2	C.h2	Sober
G.h2	C.h1	Traditional
G.h1	C.h6	Tragic
G.h4	C.h2	Warmth

Figure 6. Distribution graphs and groupings of the subjects' *Kansei* status in lifecycle of Handicraft/Furniture

Table 6. The clusters to which a subject belongs in each lifecycle stage of his/her Handicraft/Furniture

	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅
P	AFh	AFh	AHh	AHh	AFh	AFh	BFh	AFh	AIh	AFh	AFh	AFh	AFh	AIh	AHh
KU	DIh	AFh	AFh	BHh	EHh	BHh	BHh	AHh	AIh	AFh	AIh	AGh	EGh	AIh	BHh
R	0	DJh	DGh	DGh	DGh	DGh	CJh	EGh	CJh	CJh	DGh	0	DGh	CGh	CJh

The graphs (X-Y and X-Z) of distribution of the subjects' *Kansei* status in the lifecycle stages of their handicraft/furniture are shown in Figure 6. The resulted clusters are marked from Ah to Eh in X-Y graph and from Fh to Jh in X-Z graph. According to the items responded by majority of subjects belonging to each cluster, the highlighted clusters (Ah to Eh) in the X-Y graph can be characterized respectively as Fair Efficiency, Interesting/Durability, Nostalgia, Attachment and Gratification. Similarly, the ones of the X-Z graph (Fh to Jh) can be characterized respectively as Fair Efficiency, Ultimate Attachment, Fair Durability, Proximate Attachment and Nostalgia. The clusters in which each subject is laid during each stage are listed in Table 6.

4. Interpretation

4.1. *Kansei* Structure from Product Lifetime and Lifecycle Viewpoints

Overall, the *Kansei* items that have Active Emotion nature associate with the stage of P whereas the ones having Passive Affection nature associate with the stage of R regardless to the kind of product and its lifetime. The relative frequencies of positive, negative and affecting *Kansei* items relevant to mobile phone, private car and handicraft/furniture are comparably shown into three pie-graphs in Figure 7. The majority of items in all cases are positive. In the long-lived products, however, the negative *Kansei* items have been obviously decreased, while the affecting ones being increased. Furthermore, as the histograms (Figure 7) show, the relative frequencies of the affecting *Kansei* items are increased and of the positive *Kansei* items are decreased in the R stage of lifecycle of all of the studied cases of short/long-lived products.

Figure 7. Relative frequencies of positive, negative and affecting *Kansei* items in the products lifecycle

Figure 8. The levels of *Kansei* items and their structure from product lifetime and lifecycle points of view

The structure of the *Kansei* items from product lifetime and lifecycle viewpoints is visualized into a diagram shown in Figure 8. Comparing the resulted *Kansei* items all together on the basis of their belonging product lifetime and lifecycle scales, they have five different levels indicating the state of their generality/particularity. Some of the most frequent *Kansei* items belonging to each level are shown as instance in the diagram. The most general *Kansei* items such as Utility and Interest, which a user may have regarding a product regardless to its lifetime and lifecycle, are placed in the level I. The *Kansei* items placed in levels II or III are respectively

common in terms of product kind/lifetime or the stage of product lifecycle. For instance, the feelings of Efficient and Cherish that a user may have about such a long-lived product as craft/furniture during all stages of its lifecycle are in level II. But, the feelings of Appreciation, Attached and/or Regret that a user may have about any product just during R stage of its lifecycle are in level III. Level IV involves the *Kansei* items (such as Enjoy and Pout) that a user may have regarding a particular product (like his/her Private Car) during two close stages of its lifecycle (like P and KU). The *Kansei* items placed in levels V (such as Puzzled and Discovery) are the feelings that a user may particularly have about a product (like Mobile Phone) during one of its lifecycle stages (like P).

4.2. Building Models and Extracting Patterns of Subjects' *Kansei* Evolutions

On the basis of the resulted clusters indicating the subjects' *Kansei* statuses during each stage of the lifecycle of their products, the subjects' *Kansei* evaluations during the lifecycle stages of their mobile phones, private cars and handicrafts/furniture are visualized into three models respectively shown in Figures 9, 10 and 11. Each colored line between the clusters in the models represents a subject. Regarding each product, all of the extractable types of subject's *Kansei* evaluation are assorted according to their similarity in P and R stages and packed into 6 main patterns presented in the right side of the model. Considering the reversely similarity between the directions of X-Z and X-Y axis of the distribution graphs, the ones relevant to mobile phone is engaged as the base for axis order in the models, Accordingly, the ones relevant to car and handicraft/furniture are adapted to this order to be more easily comparable. In all of the models, the beginning of use generally brings Active Emotion whereas the end of use associates with Passive Affection. It should be mentioned that the subjects' *Kansei* in the stage of R is indeed about their last mobile phones or cars, which are replaced, and is chronologically happened before P and KU stages. However, the resulted models depict the probable trends of evolution of user's *Kansei* toward a mobile phone, car or handicraft/furniture during its lifecycle.

4.3. Comparison of the Patterns and Trends of PSjS in Short-lived and Long-lived Products

The subjects' eventual *Kansei* status regarding mobile phone has four different trends: Bother/Concerned; Ally; Attached; and Valid (Figure 9). The first one, Bother/Concerned, as the most ongoing trend involving most of the subjects, is a negative *Kansei* status and indicates a state of subjective un-sustainability of mobile phone, whereas the rest ones are positive and hence concerned with PSjS. The second one, Ally, is the issue of user's good partnership relation with and pleasant utility of mobile phone and can be reinforced by facilitating good partnership through software/hardware solutions. The third one, Attached or users' close affective relation with their mobile phones, can be improved by means of emotional attraction of software or appearance. And the forth one, Valid, as the issue of prizing mobile phone as a valuable or important object being still-useful and deserving to endure or be kept for a longer time, can be promoted by upgradeable software and durable hardware. Accordingly, at least two other effective means than product attachment may extend the psychological lifetime of such a short-lived product.

The model relevant to private car (Figure 10) looks more complicated than the other ones. According to this model, overall, the subjects' *Kansei* status in all lifecycle stages of the product has three main trends which all are concerned with PSjS. These trends are: concerns, satisfaction or appreciation about utility; emotionally pleasure, satisfaction or sorrow/displeasure; and affective relation/attachment. Here, the most ongoing trend involving most of the subjects can be characterized as Appreciated Utility and Attached in R stage. However, in

such an approximately long-lived product almost in all types of subjects' *Kansei* evaluation there is a level of attachment. Similarly, those levels of attachment can be causally identified with the following characteristics: utility (function/operation) satisfaction, which is almost the dominant trend; emotional pleasure; and affective relation. Among these three, affective relation is the strongest user-product attachment which may more effectively contribute to the postponement of product replacement. Nevertheless, depending on the trend or type of users' *Kansei* evolution, different means or design solutions – such as durability, upgradeability, reparability, aesthetic durability and service – can be used for extending the subjective lifetime of such a long-lived product. The model relevant to handicraft/furniture (Figure 11) looks simpler than the ones of mobile phone and private car. In this model, the subjects' *Kansei* evolution almost starts from the status of Fair Durability/Efficiency in the stage of P, while eventuating in the status of Ultimate Attachment or Nostalgia in R stage. These two eventual *Kansei* statuses indicating strong affective relation can be considered the major trends of PSjS in such a simple and long-lived product having an extremely static status but solid cultural or artistic value.

Figure 9. Various types and patterns of subjects' *Kansei* evolution during lifecycle of their Mobile Phones

Figure 10. Various types and patterns of subjects' *Kansei* evolution during lifecycle of their Passenger Cars

Figure 11. Various types and patterns of subjects' *Kansei* evolution during lifecycle of their Handicraft/Furniture

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Although user-product attachment is an effective means extending the subjective lifetime of products, the findings of this research show that there are at least two other trends than user-product attachment for promoting PSjS characterized as Ally or partnership and Valid or enduring regarding a short-lived product like mobile phone in Japan. However, the different levels of attachment might be derived from utility satisfaction, emotional pleasure and affective relation in terms of the trends of PSjS of a long-lived product like private car in Japan. But, in an extremely long-lived product like handicraft/furniture, PSjS is just concerned with strong affective relation or deep attachment that may have nostalgic nature depending on the circumstance of the end of product lifetime. As the main impact of this research, an expandable guideline for product lifetime management from *Kansei* viewpoint could be extracted from the drawn "structure and levels of *Kansei* items" (Figure 8). Overall, the positive and affecting *Kansei* items could associate with extension of product subjective lifetime, while the negative ones might associate with shortening such a lifetime. As the *Kansei* items placed in levels IV and V belong to the particular products studied within this research, they could be applied specifically for such products or a similar one to each of them from both lifetime and status points of view. But for a new product in general, the *Kansei* items placed in level III can be applied. In order to expand such a guideline and fortify its applicability, the next phase of this research will focus on the design factors associating with each level of these *Kansei* items.

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